

THE FEATURES OF EQUIVALENCE OF IDIOMATIC EXPRESSIONS IN TRANSLATION

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Abstract:

This thesis investigates the main features of the term of equivalence, translate the idiomatic expressions from one language to another. There are some rules for understanding the exact meaning of idioms while translating them in languages. The transformation theories are given according to some theorists and linguists in this article.

Key words: idiom, culture, meaningful, tradition, using in speech, authentic, communicative, factor, equivalence, theory, meaning, translation, phraseology, linguistic relation, literal meaning.

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"Equivalence is always relative in the sense that it is impacted by numerous linguistic and cultural factors," according to Baker. To establish equivalence, it is crucial to examine the suitability of the source and destination languages. There is a theory that is usually applied in translation. It's based on a theory of equivalentIt is allowed if the translation follows the back transformation rule in the original text, the contextual coherence rule in the transferring, and the transformation rule in the target text, the message is maintained, and the translation is accurate. Learners assess both the literal meanings of phrase components and their resemblance to figurative expressions in their original language when decoding the meanings of second language idioms, according to experimental studies. As a result, comparing first language and second language idioms can help learners become more aware of the cross-linguistic variation in figurative language.

To translate a material into another language, the translator must use techniques that are similar in concept and form.

Using an idiom with identical meaning and form: this strategy involves using idioms in the target language that have the same meaning as the first language.

Using an idiom of similar meaning but dissimilar:

The procedure includes translating words with the same meaning but various lexical components. Although the form is different, the translator utilizes an idiom in the target text that has a comparable meaning to the source material.

Translation by paraphrasing:

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These methods are used when there is no equivalent in the target language or when using idioms in the mother tongue is inappropriate due to the differences between the source and target languages.

Translation by omission:

When the idiom does not match the mother tongue and the meaning cannot be conveyed, omission procedures are used.

No one, however, learns a foreign language as if it were their native tongue since mastering a language necessitates cultural competency as well. They are both attentive and adaptive to their surroundings. Language expresses people's beliefs and norms fully, and because values and norms are inherently dynamic, language must evolve in perfect agreement with cultural shifts.

As a consequence, it is evident that much translating is a hit-or-miss proposition, with a meaning hit but an idiom loss. Alternatively, it is a literal-meaning hit but an idiomatic-meaning loss or loss entirely. A literal-meaning hit with an idiomatic-meaning loss is an authentic text to target text translation in which the literal meaning is attained (effectively translated), but the idiomatic meaning flavor is lost. This form of translation is known as a true hit but idiom loss.

Learning English is popular all around the world, and knowing English and being able to communicate in it is today a requirement of life. Understanding English phraseology helps to read both nonfiction and fiction much more understandable and enjoyable. The appropriate use of idioms enhances the expressiveness of speech. The English idiomatic expressions, which are not translated word for word but have the same content as the Uzbek ones when rethought, increase motivation and have a bigger impact on learning English. Phraseology is the most important and diverse aspect of any language. We may see historical evidence of language formation in idioms, as well as specific cultural and educational aspects that influenced language development. Idioms have a unique personality that makes finding counterparts in the target language extremely challenging. There are many international idioms that help identify acceptable meaning in translation, in addition to strictly national idioms in English and Uzbek phraseology. Most international idioms can help you identify the right meaning in a translating. Any language's phraseological foundation is a complicated mix of native and imported idioms, with the former definitely leading. Some idioms maintain aesthetic aspects from previous eras, which reflect the concerns of the moment. Phraseological interpretation entails the usage of stable units with varied degrees of similarity between an English language unit and the corresponding Uzbek language unit in the translation text, ranging from entire and absolute equivalent to near phraseological connection.

We will define the phraseological equivalent in order to discuss this approach of translation in greater depth. Phraseological equivalent - a phraseologism based on the translating language that is, in all other aspects, equivalent to the interpreted item. In general, depending on context, it also have the same concept and stylistic meanings, there are differences around relative idioms in concepts of meaning subject matter, stylistic possible connection, metaphor, and emotional-expressive color, they should have roughly the same element pattern, and they should have an amount of the same lexical-grammatical factors: Another is the lack of national color (for example, with reference to the necessity of odorality inanimity), belonging to the same grammatical category, usage, and link with contextual words-satellites. The

word that is produced in the meaning of a phraseological unit is derived from its use in whole or in part. Trying to comprehend someone's thinking, for example, is like to figuring out what it is. As a result, free combinations are joined to represent material that is similar to what is understood, and the device is transformed into an idiom. The approach of distribution has been used to investigate the structural and functional properties of idioms in greater depth. Furthermore, when examining idioms, it is important to consider their semantic and structural features in relation to the structure of the language's content as well as the structure of its expression. When considering the formation of phraseological units, the types of connections between their components, the nature of the linking words, and the manner of similarities must all be considered. Idioms are not just a separate component of a linguistics which can be employed or not but they are an integral part of both languages' general dictionaries. At this time, it is critical to keep track of the replenishment of the Uzbek and English phraseological funds, because idioms emerge at a rapid rate, owing to the advancement of science, the introduction of new technologies, political games, and military conflicts, all of which have an impact on English and Uzbek people. As a result, we looked at the most common methods for translating idioms in English and Uzbek. We have seen how different linguists approach similar issues differently, how different linguistic approaches are advocated, and how different viewpoints are found.

In various outcomes, different tactics may be required. However, the interpreter's personality plays the most important role here. The interpreter must be immersed in the culture of the language into which a text is being translated, and must produce the only conceivable and unique version of the translation. To accomplish so, the interpreter must include the huge body of realities of a foreign culture into his thinking, as well as communicate other people's opinions as clearly and freshly as they were articulated, while utilizing the local language's full strength and wealth.

The necessity of content adequacy when translating idioms cannot be overstated. The term "adequacy of translation" refers to an accurate representation of the original text's true meaning while adhering to the language standards. The content adequacy of idioms is greater than the sufficiency of linguistic methods when translating them. Purely linguistic patterns fade into the background during the translation of idioms. An idiom's translation entails, first and foremost, the accurate replication of the idiom's substance, as well as the restoration of its meaning through another language. Because English and Uzbek are different types of languages, there is some alteration of the original's language features during the translation process. The performance of one speech unit's functions by another speech unit is referred to as language equivalency. Furthermore, speech units can exist in two languages at the same time. The content of 'equivalent idioms' is nearly same. L. Blacksmith, who collected a vast collection of phraseological units that went beyond all the existing idiom collections at the time, is credited with one of the earliest attempts to construct a structural classification of English idiomatic idioms. M. Benson's collocation categorization resembles V.V. Vinogradov's classification of phraseological units, which emphasizes the semantic cohesiveness of mergers and unities. A. Cowie, a linguist, developed the following classification system for collocations:

- pure idioms (Pure idioms);
- figurative idioms (Figurative idioms);
- closed collocations (Restricted collocations);
- open collocations.

A. Cowie pointed out that the meaning of a collocation is made up of the meanings of the words that make it up. Because the meaning of the collocation a shattered window is the sum of the meanings of two distinct words included in it, it is characterized as an open collocation. Closed collocations, on the other hand, are distinguished by the fact that one of the words is not employed in its ordinary sense, as in the phrase, for instance, to jog one's memory- to remind, make one remember - esga solish. Unlike M. Lewis and A. Cowie, J. Bunce uses contrastive analysis to classify collocations based on the idea of predictable of translation. He proposes using the "predictability" collocations from one language to another as a criterion for translation predictability in language. 1. The researcher translated each of the elements of his suggested English collocations into German one by one. J. Bunce established three kinds of collocations depending on the "predictability" of the translation based on the findings of this "direct" translation:

- collocations that have a precise translation from English Uzbek, implying that they are highly predictable for Uzbek speakers studying English);
- the meaning of a direct translation into the other language differs from the original collocation's meaning in English].

Stable phrases that can reside in a variety of linguistic environments while performing the same syntactic duties. Equivalence refers to the employment of certain idioms in the same meaning and expression of the same material when translating idioms.

The main speech unit encountered by the translator when translating idioms is not a single word, but a complete and full syntagma. A syntagma is made up of a group of words that are joined into a single whole and serve as a semantic-syntactic unit.

As a result, when translating idioms, the variance method is more applicable than the invariance methods. As a consequence, the study of methods for translating English idioms into Uzbek is a distinct branch of comparative linguistics, in which the lexical layer and its characteristics are explored using phraseological units. We must choose the "vaqti-vaqti bilan" (periodically, from time to time) that contains an Uzbek language version if we want to make an effective translation.

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